

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

REPORTS FROM WORKSHOPS ON VALIDATED METHODS AND PATHWAYS AT EU, GLOBAL AND SECTOR LEVEL

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

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Deliverable description

Report on online or in person workshops to discuss proposed transformative pathways and their feasibility for upscaling to the EU and global context. The workshops also serve to introduce and validate relevant methods at the EU and global contexts for enhancing the prioritisation of biodiversity in decision-making and policy processes. There are three workshops with EU policy makers/representatives and three workshops with global business/financing leaders.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
BIOTraCes	Biodiversity and Transformative Change for plural and nature positive societies.
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CU	Coventry University
DAISY	DigitAI, technological and Social innovation mixes enabling transformation for biodiversity and equity
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
EU	European Union
EUBP	European Biodiversity Partnership
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IPLCs	Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities
ITPGRFA	International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture
KM-GBF	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NBSAPs	National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
PEF	Product Environmental Footprint
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
RTD	Research and Innovation Directorate-General
RTRS	Standard for Responsible Soy Production
RU	Radboud University
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TC4B	The Transformative Change for Biodiversity and Equity

TIESS	Transdisciplinary Institute for Environmental and Social Studies
ToC	Theory of Change
UFZ	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research
UNDROP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants and Other People Working in Rural Areas
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa

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Executive summary

- Six validation workshops were hosted between June 2025 – October 2025 with representatives from policy, business, research and civil society to discuss and validate PLANET4B's transformative methods and pathways for prioritising biodiversity in decision-making across EU, global, and sectoral contexts.
- Four of the validation workshops focused on validating PLANET4B's sector-specific transformative pathways and policy recommendations, with the aim of improving their clarity, feasibility, and policy alignment.
- Two of the validation workshops focused on validating PLANET4B's core research themes on values and behaviour, intersectionality, and transformative change, and the enabling conditions needed to improve the prioritisation of biodiversity in decision-making.
- Each validation workshop culminated in a rich collection of comments and feedback that will help to improve the clarity, accuracy and policy alignment of each D4.4 knowledge product. The outcomes of Task 4.3 will directly inform the final knowledge products under D4.4.
- Lessons learned from Task 4.3 included the challenge of ensuring adequate representation from policy and business actors whose time and input to the project was voluntary, managing quality discussion and engagement across hybrid and online formats and the importance on reflecting how well the objectives were achieved after each workshop in order to improve subsequent workshops. The lessons learned may offer valuable insights for future co-creation processes.
- Involving actors from policy, business, research and civil society in the validation of PLANET4B's findings will likely enhance the legitimacy, policy relevance, and usability of PLANET4B research recommendations.

1 Introduction

Policymakers and business actors are key agents of change in addressing biodiversity loss because they shape the systems that govern how societies and economies interact with nature. Policy instruments determine the rules, incentives and governance structures that influence how biodiversity is managed, used, valued and perceived (IPBES, n.d.). At the same time, our economies are fundamentally dependent on biodiversity because of the provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting services it provides (OECD, 2025; IPBES, 2024). For example, businesses commonly operate through complex global supply chains that drive land and resource use, often resulting in significant impacts on ecosystems (Salmi et al., 2023). However, the business sector can also play an important role in driving positive change by adopting and championing sustainable practices and behaviours (World Economic Forum, 2024).

Research also has a key role to play in unlocking ideas and solutions for how to transform and adapt our societies so that nature and society can thrive. However, there has often been a disconnect between research, policy and practice. For example, the goals, timeframes and theoretical approaches that characterise many research processes are often at odds with the need for simple and immediate solutions that can be easily taken up in policy and practice (Dwivedi et al., 2024). This is particularly true in the case of transdisciplinary research that explores complex concepts like systems change and transformations science because it often involves multiple interacting variables, context-dependent outcomes, and inherent uncertainties. As highlighted in the IPBES values assessment, this uncertainty and complexity can hinder uptake of research results in policy decision-making, which often favour clear and quantifiable results (IPBES, 2022). It is increasingly acknowledged that in order for research to have greater relevance and legitimacy in the eyes of policy and practice, research must adapt its approach from simply “disseminating” research findings, to involving societal actors in the co-creation of research results. Whilst co-creation is not without its challenges (Dwivedi et al., 2024), engaging actors from policy and practice in the co-creation of research can increase the likelihood that the research results will be taken up by those actors. In this way, co-creation can open up the possibility for research to have greater real-world impact.

PLANET4B recognises the critical role of policy and business actors as agents of change in reducing biodiversity loss and the importance of using collaborative methods to jointly identify solutions for reducing biodiversity loss. In this regard, the role of Task 4.3 was to host six workshops with representatives from research, policy and business to discuss, develop and validate a series of transformative pathways and transformative methods for improving the prioritisation of biodiversity in a range of policy and business decision-making contexts.

The purpose of this report is to provide a summary of these six validation workshops. The report begins by explaining how Task 4.3 builds on other Tasks and Work Packages (WPs) in the PLANET4B project in Section 2, followed by the methodological approach in Section 3. Section 4 provides detailed summaries of each of the six validation workshops. Section 5 reflects on the main challenges and lessons learned during the implementation of Task 4.3. Section 6 provides concluding remarks.

2. How Task 4.3 builds on other PLANET4B Tasks and Work Packages

One of the aims of the PLANET4B project has been to understand and communicate what transformative methods and pathways of change are needed to ensure that biodiversity is better prioritised in decision-making. WP1 laid the theoretical foundations for the project by researching 1) how diverse perceptions of biodiversity affect how it is communicated and prioritised in different decision-making contexts, 2) how different intersecting aspects of people's identities influence their values, attitudes and behaviours towards biodiversity and how people are implicated in biodiversity decisions as a result of their intersecting identities, and 3) what theories exist for influencing behaviours and decisions and catalysing systems change. Informed by this knowledge, Task 1.7 involved developing a transdisciplinary diagnostic framework for changing attitudes and behaviours guided by an understanding of plural knowledge and intersectionality in the context of decision-making. WP2 involved refining and adapting three categories of methods for engaging with behaviour change (framing and nudging, creative and arts-based methods, and deliberative methods). WP3 involved empirically testing the theories, frameworks and methods developed in WP1 and WP2 through a series of intensive and extensive case studies.

PLANET4B's five intensive case studies established learning communities centred on intersectional social inclusion in different localities across Europe. The five intensive cases experimented with the various theories and methods developed in WP1 and WP2 in their learning communities to test their applicability for improving how biodiversity is prioritised in decision-making. PLANET4B's six extensive case studies focused on researching the impact of different sectors on biodiversity (agriculture, trade, fashion, education and finance) and analysing what systems interventions are needed to improve how biodiversity is prioritised in those sectors. They established advisory groups consisting of experts from research, policy and business and ran a series of workshops with them to explore what changes are needed in those sectors to improve how biodiversity is prioritised.

The role of WP4 has been to synthesise the research and results of WPs1 – 3 and explore their relevance for policy and business contexts. WP4 consists of four Tasks and corresponding Deliverables as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview of Tasks and Deliverables in WP4.

Task	Task title	Deliverable title
4.1	Ensuring policy relevance through consultations with key enabling players	Entry points for upscaling findings at relevant scales identified based on consultations with key enabling players (EU policy makers and businesses)
4.2	Designing transformative pathways for the EU and global level and for specific sectors	Mapping of leverage points and transformative pathways for upscaling at the EU and global context produced for 5 sectors

4.3	Validating transformative methods and pathways with policy makers and businesses	Reports from workshops on validated methods and pathways at EU, global and sector level
4.4	Exploring transformative synergies and policy coherence	Knowledge products, including synthesis of the applicability of behaviour science and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes

When planning the implementation of WP4, UNEP-WCMC carefully considered how best to ensure that each Task in WP4 both builds on the outcomes of WPs 1–3 and contributes to the coherence of WP4 as a whole. The following sub-sections outline how the work from WPs 1–3 informs WP4, and how the individual tasks within WP4 are designed to complement one another.

2.1 Building on earlier PLANET4B WPs and Tasks to validate transformative pathways and policy recommendations

The first Task to be completed in WP4 was Task 4.2, led by CzechGlobe. Task 4.2 involved analysing the results of the systems mapping and leverage point analysis workshops (Loučková et al., 2024), which were conducted by the extensive case studies, and developing them into a series of sector-specific “transformative pathways” for the EU and global level in Deliverable 4.2 (Loučková et al., 2025). UNEP-WCMC contributed to Task 4.2 by undertaking a policy analysis to identify what “policy levers” are needed to support and enable the transformative pathways developed for each sector. When planning how best to build on the results of D4.2 in the subsequent WP4 Tasks, it was decided that Task 4.4 would further develop the transformative pathways and policy recommendations in D4.2 into a series of policy briefs (D4.4 “knowledge products”).

In practice, this involved working with the extensive case study partners to refine the “transformative actions” outlined in the D4.2 transformative pathways and then identifying relevant and targeted policy recommendations that could be taken at the EU and global policy levels to support the realisation of the sector-specific transformative pathways. It was then agreed that the validation workshops under Task 4.3 would be used as a means to validate early drafts of the D4.4 sector-specific policy briefs with representatives from policy, business, research and civil society, to help improve the relevance, clarity, and actionability of the D4.4 sector-specific policy briefs. In this way, the validation workshops would directly inform the D4.4 sector-specific policy briefs. Figure 1 provides a visual summary of the workflow of how WP 1–3 informed WP4’s Tasks.

Figure 1. Workflow of WP4 tasks and their interconnections.

2.2 Building on earlier PLANET4B WPs and Tasks to validate the policy relevance of PLANET4B's transformative methods

Another key output of WP4 is to develop a final “synthesis of the applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes” (D4.4). This knowledge-product is separate from the D4.4. sector-specific policy briefs and focuses on synthesising the results of PLANET4B’s five intensive case studies and their findings relating to the applicability of values and behaviours, intersectionality and social inclusion, and transformational change for prioritising biodiversity in decision-making, including their implications for policy. Similar to the approach used for validating the D4.4 sector-specific policy briefs, it was decided that two of the workshops would be dedicated to “validating” the results of the intensive case studies with representatives from policy, practice, research and civil society. The rationale for this was to ensure that the D4.4 knowledge product focused on “synthesising the applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for EU and global processes” is not only grounded in the findings of the case studies, but also informed by the knowledge and perspectives of actors with relevant expertise on values and behaviours, intersectionality and social inclusion, and the applicability of these concepts in the context of decision-making.

Whilst the final conclusive results of the intensive case studies were not yet finalised at the time that WP4 was hosting these validation workshops, there was already a growing body of evidence documenting observations by the case study partners in their learning communities, which offered insights on the transformative potential of PLANET4B’s frameworks and methods for improving the prioritisation of biodiversity

in decision-making. This body of evidence was mainly gathered during the “impact mapping” workshops conducted with case studies by Coventry University and Martin Luther University and by reviewing a number of other project deliverables to gather insights. Whilst the main deliverable detailing the results of the intensive case studies in the form of “transformative change stories” (D3.3) was not available until month 35 of the project, by gathering findings from other project sources, WP4 was able to use these preliminary findings as the basis for discussing and validating the results of the intensive case studies regarding the “applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity” (D4.4).

Figure 2. Workflow of activities contributing to the D4.4 synthesis on behaviour change and intersectionality.

3. Methodological approach to planning and conducting the six validation workshops

Between June 2025 – October 2025, UNEP-WCMC and Task 4.3 collaborators hosted six validation workshops with representatives from policy, business, research and civil society. The four validation workshops that were dedicated to validating the sector-specific transformative pathways and policy recommendations were hosted as stand-alone workshops. A key reason for this was the fact that each workshop was intended to validate the transformative pathways and policy recommendations for a particular sector-specific D4.4 policy brief. For this reason, an important requirement for these workshops was for participants to have adequate expertise in the specific sector (trade, agriculture, finance, textiles) that was the focus of the workshop discussion. For the two workshops that focused on validating the policy relevance of PLANET4B’s transformative methods, two separate validation workshops were held involving different participants. The intention behind this was to capture a wide range of views and perspectives from a broad pool of workshop participants. The results from both

validation workshops were combined together to feed into the D4.4 knowledge product focused on “synthesising the applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for EU and global processes”. Although the validation of transformative pathways and transformative methods took place in separate workshops, all of PLANET4B’s core research themes (values and behaviour, intersectionality, leverage points and transformational change) were intentionally incorporated into the discussions in all six workshops.

Table 2. Overview of validation workshops.

Workshop	Date	Location	Target Group	Number of Participants
3.1 Trade Sector	02/07/25	Hybrid: Cambridge, UK (in-person) and online	Academics, policy experts, civil society representatives, sustainability practitioners	25
3.2 Agrobiodiversity	24/09/25	Online	Agrobiodiversity conservation experts, EU agricultural policy, seed legislation, grassroots initiatives	11
3.3 Finance Sector	25/09/25	Online	Policy-finance experts, ESG policy, economist and policy-interface researchers	10
3.4 Textile Industry	2/10/25	Online	Academic researchers, international agencies representatives, industry practitioners, civil society policy experts	11
3.5 Transformative Change Cluster	29/07/25	Online	Representatives from Horizon Europe Transformative Change cluster projects	7
3.6 PLANET4B Final Consortium Meeting	10–11/09/25	Hybrid: Brussels, BEL (in person) and online	PLANET4B partners (World Café); External experts from academia, EC, international research networks (Expert Panel)	World Café: 43; Expert Panel: 4 panellists + additional participants

Following this outline of the composition of the six validation workshops, the subsections below provide further detail on the methodological approaches used in the planning and implementation of the workshops.

3.1 Preparatory work in the lead-up to the workshops

A systematic approach was used to plan and prepare for each validation workshop. Whilst the approach to planning varied depending on the format of the workshop, the following list broadly summarises the steps taken during the planning of the workshops:

- 1) **Initial brainstorming with partners:** To kick-start the planning process for each workshop, UNEP-WCMC contacted the relevant project partner to confirm their support to co-deliver the workshop, brainstorm ideas on the purpose and format of the workshop, identify suitable workshop participants and agree a suitable date and time.
- 2) **Agenda development:** Next, UNEP-WCMC produced a draft agenda for the workshop, which was then refined through consultation with the project partners involved in the co-delivery.
- 3) **Pre-workshop planning calls:** UNEP-WCMC held planning meetings with project partners to advance the draft agenda and participant list, coordinate on the development of presentation slides, and discuss roles and responsibilities in the workshop.
- 4) **Circulation of invitations to participants:** UNEP-WCMC distributed personalised invitations to participants 3 weeks prior to the workshop. For each workshop, an internal participant list was used to monitor which participants were planning to attend. The invitations sent to participants included:
 - Invitation to join the expert workshop
 - Title of the workshop, date, time and format (online/hybrid)
 - Purpose and objectives of the workshop
 - Explanation of what we wanted from the participants prior to the workshop (pre-reading) and during the workshop (active participation in the discussion)
 - Request to RSVP, and in the case that the invitee could not attend, to suggest other suitable participants from their organisation or network
- **Distribution of research consent forms and pre-reading:** For the events focused on validating the transformative pathways and policy messages, once confirmation of attendance was received from participants, they were sent a research consent form and the relevant draft policy brief for pre-reading before the workshop.
- **Preparation of online software and workshop materials:** Prior to the workshop, UNEP-WCMC set up the relevant online meeting software and developed any supporting materials that would be used during the workshop (PowerPoint slides, Miro board).

Participants for the validation workshops were carefully selected to ensure diverse expertise and perspectives relevant to each sector-specific output. Selection criteria prioritised individuals who could validate the findings from a technical point of view, assess policy feasibility and alignment, and represent the perspectives of those who would ultimately use, implement, or be affected by the recommendations.

For each workshop, personalised invitations were sent to experts spanning academic research, policy design and implementation (EU and national levels), civil society, advocacy, and, where applicable, business actors and industry practitioners. This

composition was designed to ensure that feedback reflected multiple viewpoints and that recommendations would be robust across different implementation contexts. Geographic diversity was also considered, particularly for workshops addressing global systems such as textiles, trade and finance, to incorporate perspectives from both producer and consumer regions.

Participant selection was jointly planned with partners to ensure the right mix of external experts whose insights could complement and validate the project team's research findings. On UNEP-WCMC's side, recommendations for participants were sought from internal colleagues at UNEP-WCMC who worked more directly with actors working in the trade, agriculture, textile and finance sectors. For the workshops which aimed to validate the transformative pathways for the trade, finance, agriculture and textile industries, participants were also selected from the extensive case studies' advisory groups, given the benefit of having input from experts who were already familiar with the case studies' research.

3.2 Data collection and analysis

The contributions made by participants during the workshop were captured using multiple tools depending on what was most suitable for the format of the workshop. For online workshops, digital collaboration tools (Miro boards and shared Google documents) enabled real-time documentation of participant contributions, which were systematically organised according to themes or recommendations. For hybrid workshops, both physical flip charts/post-it notes and digital tools were used to ensure all voices were captured regardless of the mode of participation. For all workshops, UNEP-WCMC arranged dedicated note-takers to record the discussion in real time.

Following each workshop, UNEP-WCMC collated all the data provided by participants during the workshop. The data was then analysed to identify areas of consensus and divergence and prioritise comments according to their relevance for informing and improving the various knowledge products in D4.4. This data was analysed in relation to existing research and case study data from PLANET4B to ensure that any changes to the D4.4 knowledge products did not compromise the key findings and messages from PLANET4B. In this way, the D4.4 knowledge products could be grounded in both PLANET4B's research evidence and practical expert validation.

Figure 3. Validation workshop data collection and analysis process.

4. Summary of six validation workshops on transformative methods and pathways

The following section provides further detail on each of the six workshops conducted under Task 4.3. For each workshop, the summary includes: the overall purpose and specific objectives, a description of participants and rationale for their selection, detailed agenda description, supporting materials used during the workshop and key outcomes, and next steps outlining how the workshop feedback was integrated back into the final D4.4 knowledge products.

4.1 Validation workshop on transformative pathways for the trade sector

Workshop description

This PLANET4B validation workshop convened experts to refine the policy brief focused on EU–Brazil agricultural trade aiming to transform agricultural trade systems to deliver more just and sustainable outcomes. The workshop was designed in a hybrid format to enable broad participation from experts across different geographical locations and sectors, including those who could not travel to Cambridge to attend the workshop in-person. This format was chosen to maximise engagement from international perspectives, particularly from the Global South, which is essential for validating work on global trade systems. The workshop structure combined presentations, “flash reflections” from participants, and group discussions to ensure diverse inputs informed the refinement of the “policy challenges” and “policy options” in the trade-specific policy brief.

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- Validate and refine the transformative pathway and “policy options” for the trade sector developed as part of D4.4.
- Explore leverage points for reframing trade policy for more positive justice, equity, and biodiversity outcomes.
- Share next steps for developing the trade-specific policy brief and plans for dissemination.

Workshop participants

The hybrid workshop took place on 2 July 2025 and was co-organised by UNEP-WCMC and Radboud University. It convened 25 participants representing diverse expertise and geographical contexts, essential for validating the global trade pathways developed by Radboud University as part of their case study based on 2 – 3 years of research. Participants included academics specialising in trade policy and sustainable development, policy experts from European and international research institutions, civil society representatives from environmental and development organisations, practitioners from consulting firms focused on sustainability, and UNEP-WCMC staff working on the trade-biodiversity nexus. The group encompassed perspectives from the EU, Brazil, India, and other regions, ensuring that discussions reflected both producer and consumer country viewpoints on agricultural trade transformation.

Description of the agenda

The 3-hour hybrid workshop was designed to facilitate discussion, validation and knowledge co-development across in-person and online participants (see Table 3).

UNEP-WCMC chaired the workshop and facilitated the breakout group discussions. Radboud University presented the transformative pathway for the trade sector and the associated “policy recommendations”. Both UNEP-WCMC and Radboud University actively participated in the workshop discussions.

Table 3. Agenda for the validation workshop focused on the transformative pathways and policy options for the trade sector.

Session	Duration	Description
Opening and Context	35 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to PLANET4B and the purpose of the workshop • Presentation from Radboud University on the transformative pathway for the trade sector • Presentation from researcher at UNEP-WCMC on “pathways for just and sustainable trade” • Participant introductions
Initial Reflections	30 min	Brief inputs from participants across sectors and geographies
Breakout Discussions	80 min	Group 1: Reviewing the list of “policy options” for accuracy, credibility and policy relevance Group 2: Reviewing leverage points and addressing gaps
Reconvening and Closing	60 min	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reporting back on group discussions in plenary • Presenting next steps following the workshop

Opening and context

To set the scene for the workshop participants, UNEP-WCMC presented a brief introduction to the PLANET4B project followed by the purpose, objectives and expected outcomes and agenda for the workshop. Following this opening presentation, all workshop participants were invited to briefly introduce themselves. The case study team at Radboud University then delivered a presentation on the transformative pathway and “policy options” for the trade sector, drawing on their case study research and the results of D4.2. Next, a researcher at UNEP-WCMC shared the findings from a similar research project they had conducted on “pathways for just and sustainable trade”, to highlight synergies with the transformative pathways and “policy options” in D4.2 and D4.4. To help set the scene for the workshop participants, both presenters were asked to address three guiding questions: What is the problem statement that the findings try to address? What actions or leverage points does your work identify? What policy recommendations emerge, and who are the primary audiences? A short Q&A session followed to ensure all participants understood the scope and content of both outputs.

Flash reflections

Participants were then invited to share 3-minute “flash reflections” to spark dialogue and surface initial reactions before the structured group discussions. This segment was designed to capture diverse viewpoints across disciplines, sectors, and geographies, ensuring that practical experience, policy expertise, and academic analysis informed the workshop discussions. Inviting “flash reflections” from participants early in the workshop proved to be an effective way of inspiring engagement ahead of the group

discussions and eliciting diverse perspectives from the workshop participants. The flash reflections also helped to reveal areas of resonance and divergence that would be further explored in the group discussions.

Breakout group discussions

The main event of the workshop was the expert group discussions. The breakout group discussions consisted of two parallel discussion groups, each addressing different aspects of the transformative pathway and "policy options":

- Group 1: Focus on actors and actions. This group focused on validating the actions needed to transform trade systems to achieve more just and biodiverse outcomes. In particular, the discussion focused on refining the key actors responsible for these actions and exploring at which scales of governance these actions are most relevant.
- Group 2: Focus on intent, goals, and paradigms. Taking inspiration from the Donella Meadows' leverage points framework (Meadows, 1999), this group focused on validating the transformative pathway by discussing whether additional "deeper" systems changes are needed to unlock transformative change. Discussion focused in particular on reviewing whether any additional actions are needed to shift the goals or priorities of trade systems; change dominant mindsets or worldviews shaping trade (e.g. growth-first, extractivism, commoditisation); and change forms of power or agency to challenge and transcend dominant paradigms.

Participants had the opportunity to switch groups halfway through the allotted time, to encourage cross-pollination of ideas. The discussion facilitators took care to ensure participation from both online and in-person attendees, managing the hybrid format to create an inclusive space for all voices.

Reconvening and closing

Following the group discussions, participants returned to plenary and a rapporteur from each group summarised the key discussion points from their group discussion. The plenary discussion helped to identify areas of convergence and divergence. The session concluded with a presentation of the emerging structure for revised outputs, an invitation to join the authoring and review team, and discussion of next steps.

Supporting materials

The transformative pathway in D4.2 and the draft "policy options" were emailed to the workshop participants as pre-reading prior to the workshop. This literature also served as the basis for discussion, validation and refinement during the workshop. During the workshop, both groups used live, open Google documents for live collaborative brainstorming, with dedicated rapporteurs synthesising insights in real time.

Outcomes of the workshop discussion

This section provides an overall summary of the key discussion points that emerged from the workshop, based on the inputs from workshop participants:

1. Concrete actions and actor roles must be better defined and diversified

- Group 1 noted the importance of addressing inclusion gaps, particularly the underrepresentation of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs) and smallholder voices. There was strong support for mechanisms to facilitate their participation in international fora and national-level decision making. Examples included mentorship initiatives, knowledge-sharing platforms, and tailored financing tools.
 - Participants called for clearer and more ambitious regulatory expectations from governments (especially the EU), including due diligence and living wage standards. They noted that global initiatives such as the Accountability Framework Initiative (AFI) and the certification standard for Responsible Soy Production (RTRS), and others, need to be embedded in broader strategies.
 - They also flagged the dangers of homogenising actor categories, encouraging more precise targeting across finance, corporations, and government levels. There was recognition that consumers, investors, and coalitions each have specific roles in shifting behaviours and enabling change.
2. Deep leverage points are under-addressed in current trade policy
- Group 2 highlighted the persistence of outdated trade goals prioritising growth and scale over sustainability. Participants urged moving away from extractivism and commoditisation. Instead, they advocated for localised, context-sensitive approaches grounded in solidarity, food sovereignty, and rights-based values.
 - A dominant concern was the disconnection between financial actors, investors, and the real impacts of production. This distancing weakens accountability and contributes to inertia. Participants expressed scepticism about current traceability mechanisms, arguing that they are often superficial, opaque, or skewed toward corporate interests. Narrative shifts were seen as critical. There is a need to move beyond critique to articulate what a better system looks like, including who benefits and why. This should include a stronger focus on non-anthropocentric values and recognition of more-than-human rights.
3. Stronger narratives and framing are essential for policy impact
- Participants called for more strategic communication to engage policymakers, consumers, and financial actors. Effective messaging must connect biodiversity and equity goals with urgent policy priorities such as food security and risk mitigation. The workshop surfaced demand for a 'reboot' of trade discussions.
 - Participants proposed that UNEP-WCMC could provide leadership by reframing biodiversity as integral to sustainable trade, drawing on PLANET4B's work. Doing so could help unify fragmented agendas across environment, agriculture, human rights, and finance.

Next steps

The outcomes of the workshop discussion will directly inform revisions to the draft D4.4 policy brief for the trade sector. In particular, the comments and inputs received from workshop participants will be used to refine the wording of the "policy options" to improve their policy relevance, accuracy and credibility. The refined "policy options" will be improved on account of the inputs contributed by the workshop participants,

whose knowledge and perspectives represent diverse geographies, backgrounds and institutional knowledge.

4.2 Validation workshop on transformative pathways for agrobiodiversity and seed networks

Workshop description

This validation workshop aimed to validate and refine the draft D4.4 policy brief on agrobiodiversity and seed networks. The policy brief builds on the transformative pathways in D4.2 but goes one step further to translate the transformative pathways into associated “policy challenges” and “policy options” for unlocking the pathways of change. The workshop specifically sought to validate what actions can be taken at the EU and global policy level (which are referred to in D4.4 as “policy options”) to better enable community seed networks and grassroots initiatives to improve agricultural resilience, conserve biodiversity, and scale up climate adaptation.

The workshop was designed in an interactive online format to facilitate broad expert participation across geographical locations and sectors. The format combined structured discussions with open group exchanges to encourage knowledge-exchange and free-flow of discussion whilst also keeping things on track for achieving the workshop objectives. A "flash reflections" session was included towards the beginning of the workshop to surface initial reactions and diverse perspectives before moving into detailed analysis, creating space for participants to express immediate thoughts and reflections that might otherwise be overlooked in more structured discussion. Breakout groups were then used to enable in-depth examination of each recommendation, with groups intentionally composed to include a mix of academics, policymakers, and practitioners. This diversity was designed to ensure that feedback reflected multiple viewpoints and that recommendations would be robust across different implementation contexts. The Miro board was selected as a supporting tool to provide transparent, structured discussion whilst also capturing input in a way that could be easily analysed following the workshop.

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- Validate and refine the draft recommendations with emphasis on feasibility and accuracy
- Clarify scope, key terms, and distinctions between specific policies and agreements
- Strengthen the messaging to improve policy alignment and coherence across EU and international frameworks and clarify the primary target audiences for the brief
- Share next steps for further developing the policy brief and plans for dissemination

Workshop participants

The workshop targeted experts with specialised knowledge in agrobiodiversity conservation, EU agricultural policy, seed legislation, and grassroots seed systems. Invitations were extended to individuals who could contribute diverse perspectives spanning policy development, academic research, and practical implementation. A total of 11 participants joined the workshop, including representatives from Non-

Governmental Organisations (NGOs) working on seed policy at EU level, research institutes focused on agrobiodiversity, international policy advisors, national government officials from EU Member States, advocacy organisations, and UNEP-WCMC internal experts with research and policy expertise. This composition was intentionally designed to ensure validation feedback reflected the perspectives of those who would ultimately use, implement, or be affected by the policy recommendations.

Description of the agenda

The workshop was designed as an interactive 2.5-hour online session divided into three main sections to maximise both structured discussion and open exchange.

Table 4. Agenda for workshop focused on validating transformative pathways and “policy options” relating to agrobiodiversity and seed networks.

Session	Duration	Description
Opening and Setting Context	30 min	Introduction to PLANET4B and workshop objectives, presentation of draft policy brief’s key findings and six recommendations, followed by a “flash reflections” session where participants shared brief reflections on the recommendations
Breakout Group Discussions	90 min	Facilitated small-group discussions systematically reviewing the six recommendations using structured guiding questions to assess clarity, relevance, feasibility, gaps, policy alignment, and actionability. Miro board used for real-time collaborative feedback
Reconvening and Closing	30 min	Plenary session to report back on the main discussion points in each group, identify which “policy options” should take priority, discuss primary target audiences for the policy brief, and outline next steps

Opening and context

At the opening of the workshop, UNEP-WCMC presented a brief introduction to the PLANET4B project and outlined the purpose, objectives and expected outcomes of the workshop. After a round of brief introductions from each of the workshop participants, ESSRG presented the results of their case study research, the transformative pathways in D4.2, and the draft “policy options” from the draft D4.4 policy brief on agrobiodiversity and seed systems. These opening presentations provided essential scene-setting for the group discussion later in the workshop. Following the opening presentations, all participants were invited to provide “flash reflections” (maximum 3 minutes each) on the case studies’ research and the messages in the draft D4.4 policy brief. When giving their “flash reflections” participants were also asked to state their positionality (practitioner, academic, policymaker, EU/national government). This segment of the workshop was designed to capture immediate reactions and surface feedback before the structured group discussion began, ensuring that instinctive responses and potential blind spots were identified early in the discussion.

Breakout group discussions

The core of the workshop consisted of facilitated small-group discussions where participants worked systematically through the six recommendations captured in the D4.4 policy brief on agrobiodiversity and seed systems. The two groups were intentionally composed to include a variety of stakeholders (academics, policymakers,

and practitioners) so that diverse perspectives could inform the validation process. UNEP-WCMC facilitated the group discussion process to help manage time, keep the discussion on track and encourage participation by creating an inclusive space for diverse viewpoints. Rapporteurs captured key discussion points in preparation for reporting back in plenary. Groups used guiding questions in the Miro template to assess the clarity, relevance, feasibility, gaps, policy alignment, and actionability of each “policy challenge” and “policy recommendation”. The Miro board served as a visual and collaborative tool to organise feedback systematically, allowing participants to see evolving ideas and build on each other's inputs in real time.

Reconvening and closing

After the small group discussions, participants reconvened in plenary to compare the key points discussed in their group, identify whether there were any gaps in the list of “policy options”, and validate which target audience are most suitable for the policy brief. In the closing session, UNEP-WCMC outlined next steps for incorporating feedback into the revised policy brief.

Supporting materials

Two key materials were used to structure the discussion and capture feedback. The draft D4.4 policy brief was emailed to the workshop participants as pre-workshop reading. The “policy challenges” and “policy options” contained in the brief then formed the basis of the discussion during the breakout groups. The Miro board (see Figure 4) was used in the workshop to systematically capture participant feedback on all six findings and recommendations in the policy brief. For each “policy challenge” and “policy option”, guiding questions prompted participants to assess clarity (is it clearly articulated?), feasibility (is it realistic and implementable?), policy alignment (does it align with existing or emerging frameworks?), and gaps (what is missing?). Participants provided feedback in real-time, enabling the group to build on each other's input and identify areas of agreement and divergence. This systematic approach ensured comprehensive expert validation of each “policy challenge” and “policy option”, which was key to achieving the objective of the workshop and subsequent work to improve and refine the draft policy brief.

Finding and recommendation 4

Stronger links between formal and informal seed systems are essential, yet participatory research and collaboration between the formal and informal seed system actors is lacking in the EU. There is currently a lack of connection between actors in the formal and informal seed system and no sustained or systematic support to strengthen these relationships. Collaboration among small-scale farmers, researchers, national gene banks, professional breeders and civil society could facilitate the scaling-up of agrobiodiversity practices

Increase EU research funding to research projects that focus on multi-actor collaboration and network-building around agrobiodiversity.

Through research programs like Horizon Europe, increasing funding support to participatory, community-led research on seed diversity and agrobiodiversity would provide insight for further policy coherence. Research calls that recognize the importance of traditional knowledge systems and encourage partnerships between community seed networks, researchers, and small-scale breeders would be particularly useful. With research of this kind advanced, farmers would be more empowered to contribute to research and knowledge-sharing, contributing to the KM-GBF Target 21 and IPCC/IPBES findings that support inclusive approaches to climate adaptation.

Feasibility: Multi-stakeholder networks require sustained funding, capacity-building, and connections to research institutions. Horizon projects have been essential for influencing policy change by making implementation challenges visible at national levels, as demonstrated by the CSA project on dynamic biodiversity management.

Gaps & actionability – Social policies linking informal and formal systems are missing, particularly connections to EU social cohesion funding. While public procurement could promote agricultural diversity, member states resist procurement directives and scaling presents challenges. Integrating traditional knowledge into education may offer a more feasible pathway than food procurement.

Clarity – what needs sharpening in the wording?

Extra comments – Horizon funding enables critical monitoring work beyond national political cycles, supporting informal-formal collaborations like seed bank exchanges. While relying on political cycles for change may be unrealistic, Horizon and ERASMUS programmes offer tangible pathways to advance monitoring and collaboration.

Figure 4. Miro board format.

Outcomes of the workshop discussion

The workshop generated substantial feedback for improving the draft policy brief. There was broad agreement on the list of “policy challenges” and “policy options” in the draft policy brief, although participants raised new insights and nuance to strengthen the messages. The following summary reflects the key points raised by participants during the workshop in relation to the six “policy challenges” and “policy recommendations”:

1. The need to prioritise exemptions for non-commercial seed exchange
 - Participants emphasised the importance of exemptions rather than simplifying registration processes for non-commercial seed exchange and small-quantity sales, as simplified processes still impose significant administrative burdens. Participants also highlighted that a stronger distinction should be made between exchange for conservation purposes and sale for commercial purposes, with conservation exchange ideally sitting outside marketing rules entirely.
2. The importance of ensuring the participation of grassroots seed custodians in governance
 - Recognition of grassroots actors must extend beyond seed access to meaningful participation in governance structures, aligning with the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture (ITPGRFA) and UN Declaration on the Rights of Peasants (UNDROP) principles. This positions farmers and community networks as agents of change rather than passive beneficiaries, encompassing all actors engaged in on-farm conservation.
3. The need to strengthen existing knowledge hubs and networks
 - Participants stressed the importance of supporting and strengthening existing knowledge hubs and seed networks rather than creating new platforms. The focus should be on resourcing what works, facilitating reciprocal knowledge exchange, and linking traditional knowledge with formal education systems.
4. The need to embed genuine co-creation in research funding

- Research funding, particularly through Horizon Europe, should require genuine co-creation where farmers and informal sector actors are involved in planning, priority-setting, and evaluation with fair compensation for their contributions.
5. The need for dedicated Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) funding for on-farm conservation
- Dedicated CAP funding schemes are needed for on-farm conservation, participatory breeding, and seed exchanges. Tying funding to measurable outcome targets for on-farm genetic diversity would provide accountability, with agrobiodiversity explicitly framed as strategic for the EU's climate, food, and biodiversity goals.

Next steps

Following the validation workshop, UNEP-WCMC conducted a detailed analysis of the contributions received during the breakout group discussions. This feedback was reviewed against the case studies' pre-existing research and analysis based on case study materials from D4.2. The revised recommendations will be incorporated into the final D4.4 deliverable, strengthening its actionability, policy relevance, and potential for real-world impact in shaping EU agricultural policy to better support successful agroecological practices and climate-resilient food systems.

4.3 Validation workshop on transformative pathways for the finance sector

Workshop description

This validation workshop, held on 25 September 2025, aimed to validate and refine the draft D4.4 policy brief entitled "*Sustainable Finance and Cognitive Biases: Theory of Change for Aligning Investment Behaviour with Environmental Sustainability Objectives.*" The policy brief was developed by UNEP-WCMC as part of D4.4, building on the case study research undertaken by the Norwegian Institute for Nature Research (NINA) and the transformative pathways developed collaboratively with CzechGlobe in D4.2. The core component of the policy brief is a Theory of Change (ToC) which illustrates a logical progression for addressing cognitive bias in the finance sector by linking desired impacts with relevant activities, outputs and outcomes. The purpose of this workshop was to validate the draft ToC with expert participants, to the aim to improve its relevance, accuracy and credibility in the final draft of the policy brief.

The workshop was designed in an interactive online format to facilitate expert discussion across the financial sector, research community, and policy sphere. It convened 5 participants, with the small number being deliberate given the complex ToC framework, which necessitated deeper engagement with fewer participants.

The session structure was organised in a format that was most conducive for systematically reviewing the different elements of the ToC (impacts, long-term and intermediate outcomes, outputs, and activities), with the main of ensuring the causal logic was clear, credible, and actionable. UNEP-WCMC chaired the workshop and facilitated the breakout group discussions. Both UNEP-WCMC and NINA participated actively in the workshop discussions.

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- Refine a draft Theory of Change that aims to effectively outline pathways for transformative change in the EU sustainable finance sphere by addressing investor cognitive biases
- Share next steps for further developing the Theory of Change and associated policy brief

Workshop participants

The workshop convened 10 participants, selected for their expertise in sustainable finance, behavioural economics and EU financial regulations. The range of expertise among the workshop participants helped to ensure that their inputs addressed the feasibility and policy applicability of the ToC framework. Participants included representatives from multilateral financial initiatives focused on responsible investment, academic researchers specialising in sustainable finance and biodiversity economics, development finance practitioners, and biodiversity finance specialists. This composition ensured that feedback reflected perspectives from both the research community and financial institutions responsible for implementing sustainable finance actions.

Description of the agenda

The 2-hour online workshop was structured to enable systematic validation of the ToC, whilst encouraging open discussion across participants.

Table 5. Agenda for the workshop focused on validating transformative pathway for the finance sector.

Session	Duration	Description
Opening and Setting Context	30 min	Introduction to PLANET4B and workshop objectives, brief introductions from participants, presentation of the draft Theory of Change
Breakout Group Discussions	90 min	Facilitated group discussion to systematically review the draft Theory of Change. Miro board used for real-time collaborative feedback
Reconvening and Closing	30 min	Discuss primary target audiences and outline next steps

Introduction

UNEP-WCMC opened the workshop with an introduction to the PLANET4B project and explained the purpose and objectives of the workshop. UNEP-WCMC then presented the draft ToC, describing the logic for how addressing cognitive biases among investors could help to align investment behaviour with environmental sustainability objectives. This presentation set the scene for the validation exercise by clarifying the ToC's structure, logic, and intended purpose.

Review of ToC components

The main event of the workshop was a facilitated discussion to systematically validate and review each element of the ToC using the Miro board shown in Figure 5.

Participants examined the impacts (desired long-term change in private finance behaviour toward sustainability goals), long-term and intermediate outcomes (shifts in risk management practices, opportunity identification, and investment flows), outputs (specific products and mechanisms needed), and activities (concrete actions to produce those outputs). The discussion moved through these elements sequentially, allowing participants to assess the causal logic, identify gaps, suggest refinements, and ensure alignment across the framework. This systematic approach enabled detailed examination of how each element of the ToC connects to achieve the ultimate pathway of change.

Summary and closing

The workshop concluded with a summary of key discussion points and agreed actions, followed by next steps and closing remarks outlining how the feedback would be incorporated into the revised ToC.

Supporting materials

A copy of the draft ToC was provided as pre-reading material prior to the workshop. During the workshop, the Miro board served as an interactive tool to guide discussion through the ToC's elements and capture participant feedback in real time, enabling transparent documentation of suggested refinements to the ToC.

Outcomes of the workshop

The workshop generated fruitful discussion focused on improving the accuracy, policy relevance and robustness of the ToC. The following points reflect the main points provided by workshop participants during the discussion:

1. Participants stressed the importance of prioritising actions that shift private finance behaviour
 - There was broad agreement that the long-term impact should focus on changing private finance behaviour towards biodiversity and broader sustainability objectives.
2. The need to clarify scope and feedback loops
 - Participants stressed the need to clarify the scope between private and public finance and to include feedback loops showing how public policy and subsidies influence private investment decisions.
3. The importance of reflecting the need for improving data quality as well as diagnostic tools
 - Participants emphasised the need for more granular data and credible diagnostics across asset classes, including sovereign bonds and indices. They highlighted major gaps in assessing nature-related risks at the country level and called for consistent methodologies applicable to all investment types.
 - Participants recommended using condition-based proxies to reduce the need for costly bespoke modelling.
 - Some participants identified that sometimes condition-based proxies can be a cost-effective alternative to complex models when suitable, using observable indicators of ecosystem extent and quality to generate broad-level assessments.
4. The opportunity case

- Participants called for a stronger opportunity narrative supported by bankable examples and quantified figures to shift investor mindsets towards nature-positive investment.
5. The importance of building capacity and addressing cognitive biases
- Capacity building and tackling cognitive biases through biodiversity financial literacy, both in education and professional training, were identified as key leverage points for transformative change.
 - The need for coalitions, which draw on actor mapping and incorporate diverse knowledge systems.
 - Participants recommended actor mapping, coalition building, and the inclusion of diverse knowledge systems to make the theory of change more actionable and inclusive.

Next steps

The feedback from the workshop will be used to develop a revised ToC that better clarifies scope and system boundaries, strengthens data and diagnostic requirements with greater attention to granularity and asset class coverage, balances risk and opportunity narratives across the framework, explicitly connects to existing scenario work and standards, and highlights cognitive biases and financial literacy as key leverage points. It will also integrate actor mapping to enhance actionability. The revised ToC and accompanying insights will be finalised in the D4.4 policy brief to guide future actions by finance and policy actors.

4.4 Validation workshop on transformative pathways for the textile industry

Workshop description

This validation workshop, held on 2 October 2025, aimed to refine and validate a list of “policy challenges” and “policy options” in a draft policy brief entitled “*Addressing the Textile Industry’s Impact on Biodiversity in the EU and Beyond: A Policy Perspective*”. The policy brief was developed as part of PLANET4B deliverable D4.4, builds on the case study research conducted by project partners, the University of Pisa (UNIPi) and the transformative pathways developed in collaboration with CzechGlobe in D4.2.

The workshop was designed in an interactive online format to facilitate the participation of actors spread across Europe, whose experience and perspectives spanned business, policy, research and civil society. The workshop combined scene-setting presentations, flash reflections from participants, and facilitated group discussion. The purpose of the workshop was to validate and refine the “policy challenges” and “policy options” contained in the D4.4 draft policy brief. Specifically, the workshop aimed to improve the accuracy, policy relevance, and credibility of the “policy options” for addressing the impact of the textile industry on biodiversity through EU and global policy.

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- Refine and validate the “policy challenges” and “policy options” to ensure their policy relevance, clarity, accuracy and credibility
- Share next steps for further developing the associated policy brief

Workshop participants

The workshop convened 11 participants, including academics and UN agency representatives specialising in sustainable and circular textiles systems, business owners and industry practitioners with expertise on policy regulations that govern the textiles industry. This composition of participants ensured that discussions were informed by the perspectives of experts conducting research on sustainability in the textile industry, experts with direct experience of working in the textile industry, and experts who are advocating for sustainability in the textile sector.

Description of the agenda

The workshop was structured as a 2.5-hour online session designed to systematically review and refine the “policy challenges” and “policy options” in the draft policy brief.

Table 6. Transformative pathways for the textile sector workshop agenda.

Session	Duration	Description
Opening and Setting Context	30 min	Welcoming remarks, overview of workshop objectives, presentation of the case study research by the University of Pisa and the “policy challenges” and “policy options” by UNEP-WCMC, participant introductions and “flash reflections” from workshop participants.
Breakout Group Discussions	60 min	Facilitated small-group discussions to systematically review the “policy challenges” and “policy options” using guiding questions to prompt participants to assess clarity, relevance, feasibility, policy alignment, and gaps.
Reconvening and Closing	30 min	Re-group in plenary to discuss key points from each discussion group and identify any missing messages, followed by summary of workshop outcomes and next steps.

Opening and setting context

The workshop opened with welcoming remarks, an overview of the workshop’s purpose and objectives, and a round of brief introductions from participants. Project partners from the University of Pisa and UNEP-WCMC presented the case study research and the draft “policy challenges” and “policy options”, providing the context and setting the foundation for the group discussions that followed. Following the presentations, participants were invited to share their initial reflections on the “policy challenges” and “policy options”, which helped to bring different perspectives to the surface and stimulate critical thinking in preparation for the group discussions.

Breakout group discussions

Using guiding questions in a Miro template, participants systematically discussed and validated each “policy challenge” and “policy option” for clarity, relevance, feasibility, policy alignment and gaps. A Miro board (see Figure 5) was used to structure discussion prompts and capture participant feedback in real time. This systematic approach ensured that each “policy challenge” and “policy option” benefited from expert input, which would support their subsequent revision and improvement in D4.4.

Debrief and closing

After the group discussions, participants reconvened in plenary debrief to report back on the main points that emerged in their group and highlight any gaps in the “policy challenges” or “policy options”. The session concluded with a summary of workshop outcomes and next steps.

Supporting materials

A draft version of the policy brief was provided as pre-reading prior to the workshop and also served as the basis for discussion during the breakout sessions. The Miro board (Figure 5) served as an interactive workspace to systematically capture participants comments for each of the “policy challenges” and “policy options”. The Miro board was shared on screen during the group discussion and participants were also given a link to access the Miro directly. For each finding and recommendation, structured prompts guided participants to assess clarity (was it clearly articulated?), feasibility (was it realistic and implementable?), policy alignment (did it align with existing or emerging frameworks?), and gaps (what was missing?). Whilst participants shared their comments and feedback, a dedicated note-taker recorded their inputs in the Miro board in real-time, enabling the group to build on each other's input and identify areas of agreement and divergence.

Finding and recommendation 2

Textile products produced and/or consumed in the EU are a major driver of greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity loss and labour violations around the world.

The production of clothing and other textiles often relies on energy intensive manufacturing, water and chemical heavy processing that contribute to climate change and environmental degradation. So too does the largescale cultivation of fibres (such as cotton). Multinational textile and fashion companies, including European ones, have created and reproduced global and fragmented supply chains by de-localizing their production to regions in the Global South in an active search for low-cost labour and weak environmental protection. This increases labour exploitation, unsafe working conditions and environmental degradation. As production and consumption increase, environmental and social pressures are disproportionately felt outside of the EU.

Design more ambitious legally binding EU regulation for reducing the absolute volumes of production and consumption of new textiles globally. Work with supplier countries to support this transition.

As a global leader in sustainability, the EU could continue to set a strong example by designing more ambitious EU regulations aimed at making the global textile industry more biodiversity-friendly and socially equitable. Specifically, regulations should discourage textile production practices linked to biodiversity loss in supplier countries in a manner similar to the way the EU Deforestation Regulation prevents the sale of products linked to deforestation. Such regulations should be designed such that they respect and promote human and labour rights in the EU and abroad. It would also be important to consider that regulations of this nature are likely to disproportionately impact low and medium-income countries that have economies reliant on textile and garment production. To mitigate this, the EU could work with supplier countries to agree the terms of the EU regulations and provide the appropriate funding to support industry transition.

Feasibility – is it realistic in this political/institutional/financial context?

Gaps & actionability – what's missing to make it stronger?

Production-consumption framing: The focus on a production versus consumption binary misses the reality that most textiles consumed in the EU are produced elsewhere. Import-targeted measures could be tied to volume-reduction objectives, with re-localization mentioned as one contextual option rather than a universal solution.
International coordination: EU policy responses must be coordinated with supplier countries and other major consumption countries to ensure effective implementation.

Policy alignment – are the right policies/levels (EU/national/local) targeted?

Clarity – what needs sharpening in the wording? Remove language portraying the EU as a “leader” in sustainability. Expand the environmental scope to explicitly include pollution alongside climate and biodiversity. Ensure the text does not position onshoring as the preferred solution and emphasize that solutions must include decent work and just transition. Frame localization as one contextual option for scaling rather than the default remedy.

The EU Textile Strategy references overproduction and overconsumption but lacks specific actions to address them, potentially due to business stakeholder influence during co-creation. This gap may justify explicitly addressing growth dynamics and including specific recommendations such as regulating fast fashion marketing, drawing analogy to tobacco and alcohol marketing restrictions. “Just transition” requires precise definition tied to concrete measures such as resource allocation and job guarantees, or the term should be avoided to prevent ambiguity. The key finding should add explicit reference to pollution alongside climate and biodiversity impacts.

Figure 5. Miro board used to guide discussion.

Outcomes of the workshop

All workshop participants expressed general agreement with the draft “policy challenges” and “policy options” in the policy brief. However, a number of useful inputs were made by participants to help improve the clarity, accuracy and policy relevance of the messages. The following points capture the main points raised by the workshop participants:

1. Emphasis should be placed on the need to reduce the sheer volume of production and consumption

- Participants emphasised that current models of production and consumption are the biggest factor driving the industry's impact on biodiversity. Current EU legislation focuses on production and waste management without doing enough to challenge the logic of endless production for financial profit.
2. The global dynamic of textile supply chains require multilateral policy responses
 - Since most textiles consumed in the EU are produced outside of the EU, it's important to work with both supplier countries and other consumer countries to collectively take action to reduce the environmental impact of the textile industry. Policies must integrate biodiversity regulation with just transition principles and avoid disproportionately burdening informal sector workers.
 3. Holistic lifecycle approaches are essential
 - Volume is the primary problem, made worse by the use of harmful chemicals and highly polluting production methods. Regulation must address the entire supply chain, from the raw materials used, to processing (chemicals and finishing methods), and end-of-life management.
 4. Implementation must avoid burdening micro and small enterprises
 - Disclosure and reporting processes create heavy administrative burdens for micro and small SMEs while large companies have more resources to comply. Participants stressed that regulations must not hinder SMEs and that any simplification of frameworks must preserve or strengthen environmental ambition. Enforcement and policy coordination should be positioned as overarching enabling conditions, with stronger scrutiny focused on actors with large biodiversity impacts and unregulated supply chains.
 5. Evidence generation must link to systemic interventions and industry engagement
 - Strengthening the evidence base calls for funding and investment into sustainability and circularity in the textile industry. However, research alone is insufficient if growth logic remains unaddressed. Therefore, research must also engage companies and SMEs directly to ensure findings are actionable and more likely to be taken up.
 6. Consumer responsibility must be accompanied by regulatory measures
 - Participants cautioned against placing primary burden on consumers, emphasising that responsibility rests with brands, producers, and systemic drivers of consumption. Interventions targeting consumers must be accompanied by policy measures aimed at reducing the volume of production. Specific regulatory levers are needed to address e-commerce dynamics (excessive returns, online marketing, personalised pricing, buy-now-pay-later services) and to strengthen bans on destruction of unsold textiles while minimising loopholes.

4.5 Validation workshop on transformative methods with Transformative Change Cluster projects

Workshop description

This joint PLANET4B-DAISY validation workshop, entitled *"Turning on Transformation: Compiling Joint Policy Messages,"* was organised by UNEP-WCMC, Martin Luther University (MLU) and Coventry University (CU) on 29 July 2025. The purpose of this workshop was to validate PLANET4B's research findings and to identify synergies between the findings and messages of the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects to help inform the messages in the D4.4 knowledge product focused on "synthesising the applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into EU and global policy processes".

The workshop was structured to encourage expert reflection from Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects about their project's findings on values and behaviours, intersectionality and social inclusion and transformational change. The discussion also focused on sharing insights on what projects had uncovered about the "enabling conditions" needed to improve the prioritisation of biodiversity in decision-making. Given that the Transformative Change Cluster projects are researching transformative change for biodiversity through a range of different lenses, UNEP-WCMC felt that the best framework for discussing and validating connections between our research findings was by discussing them in relation to the "five complementary strategies to bring about transformative change" identified in the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment (IPBES, 2024b: 35).

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- To map findings from the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects against IPBES' five complimentary strategies for bringing about transformative change to help validate the research messages in D4.4 and strengthen synergies across project results
- To discuss potential policy entry points for disseminating findings from PLANET4B and other Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects

Workshop participants

The workshop brought together seven projects from the Horizon Europe Transformative Change cluster, including representatives from PLANET4B, DAISY, BioAgora, BIONEXT, Mosaic, TC4BE, Transformative Pathways, BIOTRaCeS, CIRCIVE. The workshop was jointly organised and facilitated by UNEP-WCMC, Martin Luther University, and Coventry University (by PLANET4B and DAISY).

Description of the agenda

The 90-minute online workshop was structured in three parts to maximise knowledge exchange, group reflection and discussion.

Table 7. Agenda for validation workshop with Transformative Change Cluster projects.

Session	Duration	Description
Opening and Scene-Setting	30 min	Presentations from DAISY and PLANET4B on methods for translating research on transformative change into policy-relevant findings and messages.
Strategic Discussion	50 min	Facilitated discussion to exchange knowledge and findings across projects, explore synergies between findings, and identify options for amplifying joint messages for policy.
Closing Remarks	10 min	Summary of the main discussion outcomes.

Opening and scene-setting

The session opened with two presentations designed to illustrate different approaches for translating transformative change research findings into policy messages within the cluster. First, researchers at the Helmholtz-Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ) involved in the DAISY project presented their methodology for assessing policy innovation through a transformative lens. Next, UNEP-WCMC presented their own methodology for analysing the results of PLANET4B's case studies to identify the "enabling conditions" that were key to transformational change in the case study learning communities and how these enabling conditions were then translated into clear and targeted actions that could be taken at an EU policy level to create the necessary enabling conditions to unlock transformative change for biodiversity. This was followed by an open exchange where workshop participants were free to ask questions or highlight similar insights from their own projects.

Facilitated group discussion

The facilitated group discussion was focused on discussing and validating findings across the Transformative Change Cluster projects in relation to the five complimentary strategies for bringing about transformative change. The five complimentary strategies for bringing about transformative change consist of:

1. Conserve and regenerate places of value to nature and people
2. Drive systemic change in the sectors most responsible for biodiversity loss and nature's decline
3. Transform economic systems for people and nature
4. Transform governance systems to be integrative, inclusive, accountable and adaptive
5. Shift societal views and values to recognise human-nature interconnectedness

The rationale for using this framework is, firstly, because the five complimentary strategies for bringing about transformative change link well to the research topics across the Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects, providing a common framework for discussion and comparison whilst leaving room for the individuality of each project. Secondly, given that IPBES assessments are designed to provide policy-relevant information to support informed decision-making, discussing the findings across the respective Transformative Change Cluster projects in relation to the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment ensured that our discussions could

build on the policy-relevant findings in the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment. During the facilitated discussion, participants were given direct access to the Miro board to add their inputs. There was also a dedicated note-taker recording participants' spoken inputs.

Closing remarks

The session concluded with a summary of the main insights and messages that emerged during the facilitated discussion and next steps for developing PLANET4B's D4.4 knowledge product focused on synthesising behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity in EU and global processes.

Supporting materials

For supporting materials, IPBES' five complementary strategies for bringing about transformative change were mapped onto a Miro board, with corresponding text boxes to record participants' inputs on how their project findings aligned with specific strategies and sub-strategies.

Outcomes of the workshop

The workshop generated interesting insights on the synergies across Cluster projects relating to values and behaviour, intersectionality and social inclusion and transformation change. The following points summarise participants inputs during the group discussion.

1. Strategic entry points require multi-level engagement
 - Discussion revealed important considerations for maximising policy influence through targeted engagement. Rather than focusing solely on EU-level actors, participants suggested that national-level representatives, particularly those from Member States who participate in Council negotiations, could serve as strategic audiences for the messages. For projects with local-level empirical work, such as PLANET4B's case studies, connecting findings to national representatives may provide more direct pathways for influence by demonstrating how local transformative change evidence can inform national policy positions. The European Biodiversity Partnership (EUBP) and BioAgora platform were suggested as additional entry points for dissemination and engagement of the policy note.
2. The need to ensure that the narrative and framing of our messages emphasises risk over trade-offs
 - A critical insight concerned the importance of framing transformative change in relation to risk rather than trade-offs. Participants emphasised that our messages should challenge the false dichotomy between nature and economy by demonstrating that failing to invest in transformative change research represents a greater risk to both biodiversity and economic stability. This framing, particularly in the context of current EU priorities around competitiveness, may resonate more effectively with policymakers concerned about economic resilience. The workshop highlighted the need to address emerging narratives around competitiveness, simplification, and innovation, exploring what these mean for biodiversity and how transformative change research can

contribute to policy priorities such as those from the Multi-annual Financial Framework.

3. IPBES strategies provide an effective framework for comparing results across Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster projects
 - The mapping exercise using the five transformative change strategies identified in the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment proved valuable for organising PLANET4B's findings in ways that connect to established knowledge on transformative change. Participants identified synergies across Cluster projects and recognised opportunities to build on each other's evidence.

Next steps

The insights and messages gathered during this workshop informed the subsequent validation workshop held during PLANET4B's final consortium meeting (10–11 September 2025), during which internal partners validated and an expert panel provided a reflective discussion on PLANET4B's key messages on values and behaviour, intersectionality and transformational change.

4.6 Validation workshop on transformative methods and transformative pathways at the PLANET4B final consortium meeting

Workshop description

At the PLANET4B final consortium meeting (9–11 September 2025), a two-part process was carried out to internally and externally validate and reflect on PLANET4B's key messages on values and behaviour, intersectionality and transformational change. An in-person format was chosen for this workshop, taking advantage of the occasion of the annual consortium meeting to get participants together in person to engage in quality discussion and reflection. The first aspect of the workshop was an internal World Café session with 35 PLANET4B project partners. The purpose of the World Café activity was to discuss, validate, refine and expand on the pre-identified messages across three thematic tables, identifying both points of consensus and areas for improvement in communicating PLANET4B's research findings.

The following day, an expert panel brought together four experts whose knowledge spanned across research and policy. Panellists included a representative from the European Commission, an author in the IPBES Transformative Change Assessment, an expert involved in multiple Transformative Change Cluster projects and a behavioural science expert. Questions for the panel were shaped using PLANET4B's validated research messages from the World Café. Discussions focused on making transformative change practical and scalable, addressing systemic barriers to transformation change, and strengthening procedural justice and inclusion in biodiversity governance. Together, these activities provided critical feedback to refine PLANET4B's final key messages, validated their relevance across scales, and generated actionable insights for the D4.4's knowledge products focused on "*Synthesising the applicability of behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity in decision-making*".

Objective(s) of the workshop:

- Validate and refine PLANET4B’s key messages on intersectionality, behaviour and values, and transformative change with PLANET4B partners building on prior analysis of the intensive case studies’ results
- Engage external experts to discuss and connect the findings to EU and global policy frameworks and explore implementation pathways.

Workshop participants

The workshop brought together people who could validate and contextualise PLANET4B’s findings across contexts.

- World Café (10 September 2025): Around 43 PLANET4B partners from all work packages and case studies.
- Expert panel (11 September 2025): Four invited experts from academia, the European Commission, and international research networks. PLANET4B partners, external stakeholders, and online participants took part in an open discussion following the panellists’ interventions. Their participation helped validate the research messages and connect them to action.

Description of the agenda

The validation process consisted of two complementary sessions held over two days during PLANET4B's final consortium meeting.

Table 8. World Café and Expert Panel Agendas.

Session	Duration	Description
World Café (Day 1)	45 min	Participants rotated through three themed tables (values and behaviour, intersectionality, transformational change) in 15-minute rounds, providing feedback on pre-drafted key messages. Each table had a facilitator and a note-taker.
Expert Panel (Day 2)	60 min	Four-person hybrid panel discussing how to make transformative change practical and implementable, with guiding questions and open discussion with the audience.

World Café structure

A World Café format was chosen because of its effectiveness for encouraging active listening, reflection on others' ideas, and deep engagement with group discussion, enabling partners to share perspectives based on their unique experiences in the project. During the World Café, participants rotated through three themed tables in 15-minute rounds. The topics on each table related to the core themes addressed in the PLANET4B project:

- Table 1: Values and behaviour
- Table 2: Intersectionality
- Table 3: Transformational change

Each table had a dedicated facilitator and note-taker. Participants reviewed the pre-drafted key messages, which were drafted by the UNEP-WCMC team through a

thematic analysis of different WP deliverables. The participants provided feedback via oral discussion and post-it notes to refine, agree, disagree, modify, and add to the research messages. They were encouraged to link their reflections to specific case study examples where applicable. In each round of discussion, the points raised by the previous group were shared with the new table participants to encourage reflection whilst also leaving space for new discussion points to emerge.

Expert panel structure

This 60-minute hybrid event featured two in-person panellists and two remote panellists, with discussion guided by a UNEP-WCMC chair (in person). Following the World Café, UNEP-WCMC collated the key messages identified during the discussion and formulated questions for the panellists based on those messages. Following brief biographical introductions, each panellist responded to the question: "How can we make the concept of transformational change feel more practical and possible to implement for the benefit of biodiversity and people?"

The remaining guiding questions addressed: scaling local results, promising research areas and future directions, overcoming short-term thinking, and positioning biodiversity messages within competitive policy environments. Discussion then opened to panel cross-commentary, followed by 15 minutes of open questions from in-person and online participants.

Supporting materials

Prior to the World Café exercise, UNEP-WCMC gathered all existing project materials offering insights about the results of the intensive case studies relating to values and behaviours, intersectionality and transformational change. UNEP-WCMC then conducted further thematic analysis of the materials to extract main findings and research messages relating to values and behaviour, intersectionality and transformational change. This analysis mostly drew on the results of workshops that MLU had conducted with each of the case studies previously to better understand their transformative interventions, the impacts of their interventions and the important enabling conditions that were key to the success of the transformative interventions.

Using the results of the thematic analysis, a series of key messages were drafted for each of the three discussion themes: values and behaviour, intersectionality and transformative change. During the World Café session, the pre-drafted key messages on intersectionality, behaviour and values, and transformative change were provided on each table to support the discussion. Facilitators guided the discussions while dedicated note-takers captured feedback on worksheets in real-time. Where possible, participants were encouraged to link their reflections and messages with concrete examples from their research or case studies. In each rotation, the points raised by the previous group were shared with new participants to build on the existing discussion points, whilst leaving room for new discussion points to emerge.

For the expert panel, UNEP-WCMC collated the key messages and findings identified during the World Café and formulated questions for the panellists based on those messages and findings. Questions addressed positive examples of local transformative change, ways to engage with values in order to challenge dominant paradigms, strategies to navigate continual shifts in policy, and to position biodiversity narrative within the context of "EU competitiveness".

Outcomes of the workshop:

1. Intersectionality requires broader framing and inclusive knowledge production
 - World Café discussions confirmed that intersecting identities such as class, education, age, gender, race, migration, beliefs, and culture influence engagement with biodiversity. Participants recommended broadening beyond narrow demographics by replacing "religion" with "beliefs, worldviews, culture" and adding missing dimensions such as land tenure and caste. A critical recommendation was to call for the inclusion of affected communities in knowledge production processes and to target messages at decision-makers who control resources rather than only at communities themselves.
2. Values and behaviour interventions must address structural barriers alongside individual action
 - Participants affirmed the need to ground interventions in everyday life through immersive, accessible, co-designed experiences. However, they flagged barriers such as lack of resources to sustain actions in the community. Participants emphasised that business accountability must include clear timelines and binding commitments rather than aspirational goals alone, recognising that behaviour-focused interventions must be accompanied by regulatory incentives.
3. Genuine transformation requires multi-level approaches and realistic timeframes
 - Participants highlighted that multi-level approaches are needed, for example quick policy wins alongside long-term cultural shifts. Participants stressed that genuine transformation involves conflict and redistribution, not just consensus-building. Structural constraints such as debt and market pressures limit individual agency, highlighting the need for system mapping to precede intervention design. Timeframes for transformation should be realistic and span decades. Critically, participants cautioned against labelling incremental changes as "transformative," emphasising the need to distinguish between incremental change and fundamental system change.
4. Scaling requires addressing structural barriers and multiple spheres of influence
 - The expert panel discussions highlighted that local-scale transformation is shaped and constrained by institutional and systemic barriers. Scaling transformation requires working across multiple spheres of influence simultaneously, using regulatory tools (such as bans on single-use plastics where appropriate) alongside financial incentives. Panellists emphasised the importance of going beyond comfortable research areas to tackle monetary systems, multilateral processes, and high-impact sectors, while avoiding "transformation washing" where changes simply reproduce root causes under new labels.
5. Research structures must align with the timelines needed to unlock lasting transformation
 - Panellists identified a fundamental mismatch between short 3-to-4-year research funding cycles and the decades-long timeframes required for lasting forms of transformation. Recommendations included re-evaluating what counts as good science, recognising marginalised knowledge systems, prioritising impact over traditional academic metrics, supporting interdisciplinary and community-engaged work, and

increasing policy engagement by scientists. Transformation should be treated as iterative work that builds on efforts that are already underway rather than something that is only seen as a future goal.

Next steps

Immediate actions for WP4 included revising the key messages to reflect validated findings on intersectionality, behaviour and values, and transformative change, and incorporating panel recommendations on scaling and governance into the D4.4 knowledge product focused on “synthesising behaviour change and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into EU and global processes”. The synthesis knowledge product will integrate these validated messages and recommendations to provide evidence-based, validated knowledge that bridges local innovation with systemic transformation.

5 Reflecting on lessons learned and challenges in Task 4.3

This section reflects on the main lessons learned and limitations encountered during the planning and implementation of the six validation workshops. The reflections presented below are based on UNEP-WCMC's own observations and feedback gathered during the implementation of Task 4.3. These lessons learned may serve to inform validation activities that are conducted as part of other Horizon Europe-funded research in future.

1. Challenges of in-person and hybrid workshop formats

Bringing participants together in person proved challenging for these validation workshops. In the case of all six of the workshops, the participants were geographically dispersed across Europe and, in some cases, other parts of the world. This presented challenges for some participants, who highlighted that the time commitment and other logistical constraints made it difficult to justify attending in-person. When planning the first workshop for Task 4.3 (validating the transformative pathway and policy recommendations for the trade sector), a hybrid format was chosen. The rationale for hosting the workshop in a hybrid format, was the hope that having in-person participation would be conducive to an immersive and quality discussion, whilst still ensuring that those unable to attend in-person could participate online. However, on account of time and other logistical constraints, most participants ultimately opted to join the workshop online. This resulted in an experience that did not fully capitalise on the advantages of either format. Learning from this, subsequent workshops were hosted either fully in-person, capitalising on opportunities where participants were already coming together in person (e.g. the final PLANET4B event), or fully online. By adopting an in-person or online-only approach, the level of engagement and participation improved, and the workshop objectives were more fully achieved.

2. Iterative improvement through reflective practice

The planning and delivery of the six workshops followed an iterative process. After each session, the organising team reflected on the outcomes, identifying what had worked well and what aspects could be improved. These lessons were systematically integrated into the design of subsequent workshops. This reflective approach contributed to progressively improving the structure, facilitation, and participant

engagement, ultimately improving the effectiveness of each workshop in meeting its intended objectives.

3. Representation and participation across stakeholder groups

For the workshops focused on validating the policy relevance of PLANET4B's results on values and behaviours, intersectionality and social inclusion, and transformational change, it proved challenging to identify and engage suitable participants from policy and business backgrounds. Whilst every effort was made to adapt the language and concepts in these workshops for non-expert audiences, the highly holistic and conceptual nature of these topics meant that it was difficult to identify and engage participants from these sectors to participate in the workshops. Consequently, participation from research and civil society organisations was higher in some workshops, with lower representation from policy and business stakeholders. This aside, there were fortunately other opportunities to engage with policy and business actors about PLANET4B's research in WP4. In particular, Task 4.1 "Ensuring policy relevance through consultations with key enabling players" involved in-depth discussions with business and policy actors about the potential applicability of the project's research for informing biodiversity-related decision-making in policy and business contexts. The results of these consultations can be found in Deliverable 4.1 "Entry points for upscaling findings at relevant scales identified based on consultations with key enabling players".

This experience reflects a broader challenge identified in research on science–policy–society interfaces: while the co-creation of knowledge with multiple actor groups can significantly enhance the uptake of research in policy and practice, meaningful co-creation requires these actors to be properly embedded in the project from start to finish. This level of engagement also necessarily requires time and financial resources to guarantee their involvement. In the PLANET4B project, representatives from policy and business did not have a formal ongoing role in the project, aside from those who participated voluntarily in the learning communities and advisory groups. As a result, their engagement in the validation workshops was more akin to consultation rather than co-creation. This limited level of involvement may, in turn, reduce the likelihood that these stakeholders actively take up or implement the recommendations discussed during the workshops.

6 Conclusion and outlook

Task 4.3 set out to validate PLANET4B's transformative methods and pathways for improving the prioritisation of biodiversity in decision-making. Through six carefully designed validation workshops, Task 4.3 created a platform for dialogue between actors representing policy, business, research and civil society, all of whom are important agents of change for improving how we prioritise biodiversity in decision-making. These workshops have not only served to validate the policy relevance and feasibility of PLANET4B's findings, but they have also supported the co-production of knowledge. This knowledge is grounded in the results of PLANET4B's research and complemented by the experience and perspectives of actors who can apply this knowledge in real-world decision-making contexts.

Collectively, the findings from these workshops reaffirm the message articulated in the introduction that transformative change for biodiversity requires bridging the gap

between research, policy, and practice. By involving diverse actors from policy, practice, research and civil society in the validation of PLANET4B's findings, Task 4.3 advanced the project's objectives of ensuring the policy and business relevance of PLANET4B's results. By improving the relevance and credibility of PLANET4B's transformative pathways and methods, there is a greater likelihood that these findings will be taken up by those responsible for implementing change in policy and business contexts.

Looking ahead, the outcomes of Task 4.3 provide valuable insights for future work. Within PLANET4B, they will continue to inform WP4's efforts to synthesise and communicate the project's results in a way that is relevant for policy and business across, namely through D4.4. Beyond the project, the insights gained through Task 4.3 affirm the importance of bringing together multiple actors to co-produce knowledge. Embedding such approaches into future Horizon Europe projects and related research is essential to ensuring that efforts to unlock transformative change for biodiversity are relevant, actionable, and capable of driving transformative change at scale.

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Statement on data availability

The data used to produce this report includes data collected during the six validation workshops. The data collected as part of this Deliverable are available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17425971>.

Statement on ethics

All workshop participants provided written informed consent prior to participation, confirming their understanding that participation was voluntary, their right to withdraw, and that their data would be processed in accordance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2018). Participants were informed that their inputs would be recorded in written form and anonymised for use in PLANET4B's research outputs. No conflicts of interest were identified, and this research was conducted as part of the PLANET4B project, which does not reflect the opinions of the European Commission.